

New Types of Parachors and Some New Observations on the Friedel-Crafts Reaction*

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Mr. Chairman, Ladies, and Gentlemen,

I am very thankful to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for having done me the honour of inviting me to deliver this Eighteenth Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture. It is a custom on such an occasion to give an account of the most recent developments in a particular branch in which the lecturer is interested or to give an account of any original contribution made by the lecturer and his collaborators. However, before I give an account of the contribution made by my team-work in the subject of "New types of parachors", and "Some new observations on the Friedel-Crafts reaction", I will like to pay my tributes to the qualities of the head and heart of this remarkable person in whose memory this lecture is being delivered.

Acharya P. C. Ray was one of those distinguished personalities who left permanent impress on their countrymen by their ideals, aspirations, work, and achievement. He was born at a time when this country was passing through great upheavals. The Indian Mutiny or the First War of Indian Independence had just been ruthlessly put down by the military arms of the East-India Company. The whole Indian Nation was groaning under suppression, oppression, depression, frustration, and humiliation. As if to fulfil the veracity of the dictum of Bhagwatgita that:—

यदा यदा हि धर्मस्य क्लानि भवन्ति भारत ।
अभ्युत्थानमर्क्षस्य तदात्मानं सृजाम्यहम् ॥
परित्राणाय साधूनां विनाशाय च दुष्कृताम् ।
धर्मसंस्थपनायै संभवामि युगे युगे ॥

There were born in India at this juncture, men like Motilal Nehru, Bal Gangadhar Tilak, Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya, Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, Sir Rabindra Nath Tagore, Sir J. C. Bose, and Acharya P. C. Ray. I will specially like to mention the last three, though all these highly gifted and distinguished gentlemen revolutionised the thought and culture of India in their own way. Sir Rabindra Nath Tagore shone like a blazing resplendent sun in the firmament of literature and brought great prestige to India by winning the Nobel Prize for literature in 1913. Sir Jagdish (Sir Jagadish Chandra) Bose spread the fame of India in all quarters of the globe by his researches on short-electric waves (Hertzian waves) and the response in the living and the non-living, while Acharya P. C. Ray has

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shed the lustre of a full moon in the realm of teaching and research in chemistry in India. Of him I can say that he was the pioneer of chemical research and put India on the map of chemical research in the world. He was also responsible for building up chemical industries in India, and was the Founder-President of the Indian Chemical Society. The work that he did as an educationist, as a chemist, as a social and political worker, and as a humanist stands as a permanent memorial to his activities. The life of a recluse that he lived, of plain living and high thinking, is a gospel of inspiration to many of his less fortunate countrymen. I cannot resist the temptation of quoting Longfellow and Bhagwatgita in this respect.

“Lives of great men all remind us,
we can make our lives sublime;
And departing, leave behind us,
footprints on the sands of time.

Footprints that perhaps another,
Sailing over life's solemn main;
A forlorn and ship-wrecked brother,
Seeing, shall take heart again.”

यद्यदाचरति श्रेष्ठस्तत्तदेवेतरो जनः ।
स यत्प्रमाणं कुरुते लोकस्तदनुवर्तते ॥

Perhaps some more distinguished chemists have been born in India since then, but none has been able to capture the popular imagination as he did. As Kalidasa has said in the Raghuvansha:—

कामं नृपाःसन्तु सहस्रशोऽन्ये राजन्वतीमाहुरनेन भूमिम् ।
नक्षत्रताराग्रहसंकुलापि ज्योतिष्मती चन्द्रमसैव रात्रिः ॥

He was born on 2nd August, 1861 in Khulna District, had his primary education in a village school, and the secondary education in Calcutta at the Albert School, from which he passed his Entrance examination. He joined the Metropolitan College where he came under the influence of the great reformer Keshab Chandra Sen, and the great orator Surendranath Banerjee, who was a Professor of English. He was oscillating like a pendulum between Arts and Science, but the chemistry lectures of Sir Alexander Pedler aroused his curiosity and interest in chemistry and he decided to take up science. He passed the F. A. examination in 1881 and joined the degree course for Science. While a student of the undergraduate class he competed in 1882 for and won the Gilchrist scholarship which enabled him to join the University of Edinburgh in the same year.

His career at Edinburgh University was very brilliant, and after taking the D. Sc. degree of that University, he returned to India in 1888, full of academic honours and filled with high hopes to serve his country. He had to wait for a year before he was appointed an Assistant Professor of chemistry at the Presidency College. He remained at this college till his retirement in 1917, and became the Professor and Head of the Chemistry Department of the newly founded College of Science and Technology of the University of Calcutta till his retirement. The discovery of mercurous nitrite in 1896 was a red-letter day in his chemical career. That accidental discovery during the course of purifying mercury with dilute nitric

acid proved to be the key which subsequently unlocked the door of a veritable Aladdin's cave, where he and his research students unearthed one by one a few dozen inorganic and organic nitrites. I do not wish to go into details regarding his chemical contributions, as they have been more ably described by my predecessors, but suffice it to say that his laboratory became the nursery for training the future teachers and researchers in chemistry. Some of his research students, who distinguished themselves afterwards as professors and research chemists of international repute, are P. Neogi, B. B. Dey, N. R. Dhar, H. K. Sen, R. L. Datta, J. C. Ghosh, P. B. Sarkar, J. N. Mukherjee, J. N. Ray, P. C. Guha, P. R. Rây, P. K. Bose, B. C. Guha, and several others who carried the torch of knowledge to various parts of the country. He used to take great pride and elation in the achievements of his pupils and used to say:—

सर्वत्र जयमन्विच्छेतुत्रात्सिष्यात् पराजयम् ।

He also inspired other young chemists in different parts of the country by his shining example of single-hearted devotion to teaching and research in chemistry. It will not be an exaggeration to state that there is hardly a distinguished professor of chemistry in this country who does not owe something to him directly or indirectly in moulding his scientific career. I had the unique honour and privilege of meeting him thrice, the first occasion being in 1920. This meeting decided my career as a chemist, as I was oscillating between science and law at that time.

Side by side, Acharya P. C. Ray indulged in his keen interest of history, literature, history of science, and history of chemistry. He wrote the History of Hindu Chemistry in two volumes to show that the study of chemistry in ancient India was pursued diligently and intelligently. When this book was published, it received universal encomium abroad and was hailed as a very important contribution to the History of Science by Savants like Mareelin Berthelot, and Sylvan P. Levi. He also cherished a keen desire for the application of the knowledge of chemistry for the welfare of the country through the development of chemical industries.

In 1901, he started the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works with a capital of Rs. 800/- only for preparing common pharmaceutical products for the market from the locally available raw materials. The capital of this limited Company to-day is in terms of crores of rupees, and provides employment to thousands of skilled and unskilled workers. The growth of chemical industries in Bengal was mainly due to him and his students like H. K. Sen, A. C. Ganguly, H. L. Dey, and A. C. Datta. In 1924, the Indian Chemical Society was started, so that the Indian output of research could be published without much loss of time. He helped liberally with finance to realise this life-dream of his, and was the first elected Founder-President of the Society. This Society has played a notable part in fostering research in pure and applied chemistry in India.

He was a great patriot, and encouraged swadeshi, Khaddar, and charkha. Gandhiji's message of charkha was carried by him to every home in Bengal. He was an ardent nationalist in political views, and his dictum was "Chemistry can wait, research can wait, industries can wait, but Swaraja cannot wait." He was a friend of the downtrodden, and used to give free board, lodging and tuition fees to two or three poor intelligent students every year. In nature, he was kind, simple, generous, sympathetic, charitable and lovable. To know him was to love him. He believed in the idea of "Plain living and high thinking,"

and led the life of a recluse. He was a life-long bachelor, like the great sage Kanva of Shakuntalam and considered the student community as his family. He was their friend, guide, and philosopher, and they in turn entertained the deepest affection and reverence for him. His whole life was dedicated to the uplift and regeneration of our country as he was a staunch believer in the precept of:

उदारचरितानां तु वसुधैवकुटुम्बकम् ।

To sum up, he was great as a scholar, greater as a chemist, but greatest as a man. May his great and shining example continue to inspire us for long. Of him, we can proudly say that:

कुलंपवित्रं जननी कृतार्थी वसुधारापुण्यवती च येन ।

I now come to the question of certain scientific topics in which I have been interested during the last ten or fifteen years, and wherein, with the help of my students, I have been able to contribute something.

NEW TYPES OF PARACHORS

It has been the aim of chemists to find relationships between the structure of molecules and their chemical and physical properties. Many interesting relationships have been found, but none provides a complete answer. It is not surprising that no single physical property seems to be readily correlated with all types of differences in structure. Molecular volumes based upon densities, measured near the boiling point, were extensively investigated by Kopp¹, Traube², and Le Bas³. Definite quantitative relationships were observed and atomic values were derived to be used in an additional manner. These values have been useful in spite of certain obstacles, the greatest of which has been the difficulty of comparing the molecules in the same, or corresponding state. One effort to overcome this difficulty led to the determination of the so-called *Null-punkt's Volume*, which was obtained by the extrapolation of temperature-density curves to absolute zero by Biltz, Fischer, and Wunnenberg⁴. Another promising approach was based upon Guldberg's rule⁵. These theoretical modifications of the simple molecular volume concept, however, have been somewhat disappointing.

The most successful attempt in this direction has been the concept of *parachor* by Sugden in 1924, based on the empirical relationship discovered by Macleod⁷ among surface tension, density, and temperature. The parachor is thus a secondary derived function dependent on the primary properties of surface tension, density, and molecular weight and gives us a method of comparing the molecular volumes of different compounds at the temperature of unit surface tension. This parachor has been found to possess primarily an additive property, the parachor of a compound being the sum of the atomic para-

1. Kopp, *Annalen*, 1855, **93**, 129; **95**, 303.
2. Traube, Ahren's Vortrage, 1899, **4**, 355.
3. Le Bas, "Molecular Volumes of Liquid Chemical Compounds", Longmann's Green and Co., New York, 1915.
4. Biltz et al., *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **151A**, 13.
5. Guldberg, *ibid.*, 1890, **3**, 374.
6. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1177.
7. Macleod, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **19**, 39.

chors with some additional terms, where certain structures, such as double and triple bonds, cyclic structures, different bonding of oxygen and nitrogen, hydrogen bonding or chelation, position isomerism in alkylbenzenes, etc., are present. The chief significance to be attached to the parachor, as compared with the molecular volumes obtained by previous methods, is that this method does make some allowance for the effect on molecular volumes of the forces due to molecular attraction. The comparison of parachor with critical volume and mean collision area supplies further evidence for the view that the parachor is a true measure of the molecular volume. Mumford and Philips⁸, Vogel⁹, Quayle¹⁰, and Gibling¹¹ have modified Sugden's values of atomic parachors.

Because of the relationship observed between the parachor and several other properties, other derived properties related to the parachor have been suggested. In 1939 Bogdan¹² suggested the *neoparachor* which was a function of the molecular volume and the absolute boiling point. Friend and Hargreaves¹³ in 1943 suggested *rheochor* which was a function of viscosity and molecular volume. Bowden and Jones¹⁴ in 1948 suggested the *lyoparachor* which was a function of the internal latent heat of vaporisation and molecular volume.

As early as 1926, the author¹⁵ suggested *lambdachor*, a function of the internal latent heat of vaporisation and molecular volume. This was based on the empirical relationship existing among internal heat of vaporisation (λ_i), the density of the liquid (D), and the orthobaric density of the vapour (d) at a particular temperature. From the molecular lambdachors, atomic lambdachors for atoms like carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen were calculated. It is generally additive in character, but constitutive effects are also obtained. The values for oxygen were different according as it was in the form of a hydroxyl, an ether, a ketone, or a carboxylate ester. Double and triple bonds as well as ring-closure in the case of compounds like benzene, pyridine, naphthalene, and cyclohexane raised the values. Owing to my enthusiasm for and preoccupations with pure and applied organic chemistry, this work remained unfortunately as a portion of my M.Sc. thesis submitted to the University of Bombay, and never published. However, as there were certain minor differences between my work and that of Bowden and Jones, which was published in 1948, it was published in 1961 in the Acharya P. C. Ray Birth-centenary Souvenir number of this Journal¹⁶. In a later paper¹⁷ the author has shown that the total heat of vaporisation and molecular volume can be utilised for another type of *lambdachor* (P_λ), whereas the previous *lambdachor*, based on the internal heat of vaporisation, has been designed as the *true lambdachor* (P_{λ_i}). The relationship among the two lambdachors, Sugden's parachor (P), and critical volume (V_c) has been shown in Table I.

8. Mumford and Philips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2112.
9. Vogel, *ibid.*, 1934, 333; 1943, 363; 1946, 133; 1948, 624.
10. Quayle, *J. Amer. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 600; 1962, **64**, 1294; 1944, **66**, 938.
11. Gibling, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299, 304; 1942, 661, 655; 1944, 380, 383; 1945, 336; 1953, 146, 149.
12. Bogdan, *Bull. Soc. Sci. Acad. roumaine*, 1939, **22**, 104.
13. Friend and Hargreaves, *Phil Mag.*, 1943, **34**, 643; 1944, **35**, 57, 136, 620; 1945, **36**, 73.
14. Bowden and Jones, *ibid.*, 1948, **39**, 155.
15. R. D. Desai, M. Sc. Thesis, Bombay University, 1926.
16. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 558.
17. *Ibid.*, 1965, **42**, 536.

The empirical equations deduced by the present author for latent heat of vaporisation are :

$$\lambda^{5/7} = K(D-d), \text{ where } K \text{ is independent of temperature} \quad (\text{I})$$

$$\lambda_i^{2/3} = K_1(D-d), \text{ where } K_1 \text{ is independent of temperature} \quad (\text{II})$$

Macleod's empirical equation for surface tension is :

$$\lambda^{1/4} = C(D-d), \text{ where } C \text{ is independent of temperature} \quad (\text{III})$$

From these three equations, we can derive the relationship between latent heat of vaporisation and surface tension at the same temperature.

$$\lambda^{5/7} = K_3 \times \lambda^{1/4}, \text{ where } K_3 \text{ is independent of temperature} \quad (\text{IV})$$

$$\lambda_i^{2/3} = K_4 \times \gamma^{1/4}, \text{ where } K_4 \text{ is independent of temperature} \quad (\text{V})$$

Equations (IV) and (V) enable us to determine the latent heat of vaporisation of a liquid at any temperature if its surface tension and latent heat of evaporation at one temperature are known, and *vice versa*, and therein lies their utility.

TABLE I

Substance.	(P_λ) .	(P_{λ_i}) .	$[P]$.	V_c .	P_λ/V_c .	P_λ/P_{λ_i} .	P_λ/P .
Benzene	2456	1869	206.3	256.1	9.59	1.33	11.9
Diethyl ether	2561	1916	211.7	281.9	9.84	1.34	12.1
Ethyl acetate	2574	1902	217.1	286.0	8.99	1.32	11.9
Isopentane	2758	2081	230.0	307.8	8.99	1.32	12.0
<i>n</i> -Pentane	2816	2131	232.0	309.2	9.11	1.32	12.1
Ethyl formate	2218	1678	177.0	228.5	9.71	1.32	12.5
Propyl acetate	3085	2314	257.0	344.9	8.94	1.33	12.0
Ethyl propionate	3060	2295	252.9	343.9	8.90	1.33	12.1

Though the parachor provides a method of the comparison of molecular volumes under corresponding states, the impracticability of the measurement of surface tension over the wide temperature range necessary for the adjustment values to the same surface tension would appear to discredit the usefulness of the parachor. For most unassociated liquids, the parachor is, however, subject to only a minor temperature difference. The experimental difficulties of determining the latent heats of vaporisation of liquids over a wide temperature range limits the usefulness of the lambdachor. Any other physical property of liquids, which shows variation with density and temperature, such as refractive index, viscosity, ultrasonic velocity, dielectric constant, fluidity, vapour pressure, etc., can be utilised for comparing the molecular volumes.

In collaboration with Miss S. K. Dalal, the author⁸ has submitted to the Indian Chemical Society two papers in which the *Refractors* (P_N) of over 300 compounds have been calculated from the latest data available on refractive index for the D-line, density, and temperature. It was observed that $n^3 = K(D-d)$ where K was quite independent of temperature, and *refractor* was taken as $[P_N] = n^3 \times V_m$, where V_m was the molecular volume. The liquids belonged to the various classes of aliphatic and hydroaromatic series, such as hydrocarbons, halogen derivatives, alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, acids, esters, ethers, nitriles, amines, mercaptans, thio-ethers, disulphides,

nitro compounds, nitrites, and nitrates. The *atomic refrachors*, calculated for various elements as well as the structural constants are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
Atomic and structural refrachors for Na_p-line.

	Value.		Value.
CH ₃ -group	52.4	Sulphite group	129.5
Carbon	29.2	Sulphate group	125.8
Hydrogen	11.6	N (in primary amines)	27.7
Oxygen (OH)	18.2	N (in secondary amines)	30.6
Oxygen (ether)	19.5	N (in tertiary amines)	32.3
Oxygen (ketonic)	24.5	N (in nitriles)	33.7
O ₂ in esters	41.6	Nitric group (alkyl)	76.6
Fluorine	13.4	Nitrite group (alkyl)	83.0
Chlorine	67.1	Nitrate group (alkyl)	102.6
Bromine	101.1	The double bond	19.0
Iodine	164.2	The triple bond	24.1
Sulphur (SH)	89.0	3-Membered ring	7.1
Sulphur (sulphide)	92.0	4-Membered ring	5.1
Sulphur (disulphide)	97.4	6-Membered ring	0.0
Sulphur (thioketone)	105.2	7-Membered ring	0.0

If the refrachor (P_n) is expressed according to a linear equation :

$$p_n = \alpha M + B$$

where α is a *general constant* for all the series and is equal to $52.4/14=3.743$, and M stands for the molecular weight of the liquid, the value of B , which is a *characteristic constant* for a particular homologous series, can be calculated. These different values of B , which are shown in Table III, establish the structural effect of the refrachor. Moreover, the refrachor of any member of the series can be calculated from this equation.

TABLE III
Values of B for various series.

Series.	Values of B.	Series.	Values of B.
Alkanes	+16.4	Alkyl dibromide	-396.1
Alkenes	+20.3	Alkyl tribromide	-589.3
Cycloparaffins (above 6 carbon)	+1.0	Alkyl iodide	-305.0
Cyclic olefines	-1.3	Alkyl di-iodide	-588.5
Aliphatic alcohols	-25.2	Alkyl cyanide	-26.3
Cyclic alcohols	-41.2	Alkyl primary amines	-0.5
Aliphatic ethers	-23.1	Alkyl secondary amines	+1.2
Aliphatic aldehydes	-35.6	Alkyl tertiary amine	+4.2
Aliphatic ketones	-34.8	Dialkyl hydrazine	-12.1
Cyclic ketones	-50.0	Nitroparaffin	-67.3
Fatty acids and esters	-77.0	Alkyl nitrite	-77.4
Esters of dibasic acids	-171.5	Alkyl nitrate	-122.0
Alkyl carbonates	-120.5	Dialkyl nitroso-amine	-57.9
Alkyl fluoride	-50.4	Alkyl thiol	-18.0
Alkyl chloride	-58.0	Dialkyl sulphide	-13.1
Alkyl dichloride	-132.5	Dialkyl disulphide	-33.5
Alkyl trichloride	-203.9	Alkyl sulphite	-154.8
Alkyl tetrachloride	-276.0	Alkyl sulphate	-218.0
Alkyl bromide	-191.5	Alkyl thiocyanate	-55.1
		Alkyl isothiocyanate	-28.2

If the refractor (P_n^*) is a true measure of the molecular volume, it should bear an intimate relationship with critical volume (V_c) and Sugden's parachor (P). Table IV records this relationship clearly.

TABLE IV

Substance.	P_n .	V_c .	P .	P_n/V_c .	P/V_c .
Cyclohexane	312.6	301.5	244.5	1.02	0.79
Diethyl ether	254.6	281.9	311.7	0.91	0.75
Ethyl acetate	254.2	286.0	217.1	0.89	0.76
Isopentane	286.6	307.2	233.5	0.93	0.76
<i>n</i> -Pentane	287.6	309.8	231.0	0.93	0.75
Propyl acetate	304.8	344.9	258.1	0.95	0.74
Ethyl propionate	304.3	343.9	254.5	0.95	0.74
Acetone	188.7	216.6	161.7	0.96	0.76
			Mean	0.93	0.76

Table IV shows that this ratio is approximately 0.93, though it varies slightly from substance to substance. The last column shows that the ratio of Sugden's parachor to the critical volume is 0.76, though it slightly varies for each substance. Moreover, it is observed that the refractor is 1.22 times Sugden's parachor.

There is an intimate relationship among the refractor (P_n), critical temperature (T_c), boiling point (T_b), and the entropy (S) which for an unassociated liquid is about 20.78. This relationship is given by

$$[P_n] = \frac{1.22}{2} \times \frac{V_c T_c}{T_b} = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta S}}{7.5} \times \frac{V_c T_c}{T_b}$$

Table V shows these relationships. The values are fairly comparable.

TABLE V

Substance.	V_c .	T_c/T_b .	P_n	
			Calc.	Obs.
<i>n</i> -Pentane	309.8	1.52	286.3	287.6
Isopentane	307.2	1.52	283.6	286.8
Diethyl ether	281.9	1.52	260.4	254.6
Ethyl acetate	286.0	1.50	260.7	254.2
Acetone	216.6	1.52	200.2	188.7
Propyl acetate	344.9	1.52	318.6	304.8

Mean collision areas (a) of molecules of four different substances are compared with those of Sugden's parachors, refractors, and sonochors (P_s) in Table VI. The ratio in the last two columns is found to be roughly constant. Better agreement cannot be expected since many molecules are not symmetrical and $[P_n]^{2/3}$ is only a rough measure of the molecular cross-section.

The refrachor, though additive, shows susceptibility to constitutive influences to a much greater extent than Sugden's parachor. Some of these structural variations have been discovered, e.g. those of double and triple bonds, conjugation of double and triple bonds, different states of the bonding of oxygen, sulphur, and nitrogen, ring formation etc. It can be profitably used in determining the effect of hydrogen bonding, position isomerism in benzene derivatives, effect of alkyl groups, and alkyl branching. Moreover, the relation of the refrachor to other fundamental constants, such as critical temperature, critical pressure, critical volume, surface tension, latent heat of evaporation, viscosity, vapour pressure, dielectric constant, and ultrasonic velocity has been investigated. The refrachor of solids in solution can be determined. This determination encounters several experimental difficulties, and needs further investigation. The technique of determining the refrachor is much easier than that of parachor, and this point is in its favour.

TABLE VI

Substance.	$a \times 10^{16}$	$[P]^2/3/a.$	$[P_n]^2/3/a.$	$[P_s]^2/3/a.$
Benzene	13.83	2.52×10^{16}	3.24×10^{16}	6.06×10^{16}
Ethyl acetate	15.01	2.41	2.68	5.85
Propyl acetate	17.11	2.30	3.00	5.67
Methane	7.72	2.27	2.12	6.13

It is instructive in this respect to refer to the earlier work of Gladstone and Dale¹⁹ and Lorentz and Lorenz²⁰ whose concept of molecular refractivity has associated the refractive index with molecular volume at a definite temperature. Their expressions, which are known as *n formula* and *n² formula* respectively, do not, however, take into consideration the variation of the refractive index with density and temperature. Joshi and Tuli²¹ suggested the term refrachor which was a combined function of surface tension, refractive index, and density at a particular temperature. It therefore cannot be termed refrachor, which should have only the refractive index associated with molecular volume.

In collaboration with Miss S. K. Dalal and Miss P. R. Patel, the author has tried to apply this *n³ formula* to specific dispersive power or dispersivity of liquids with a view to evolving the new constant, the *Dispersechor*, and our efforts have been partly successful. The dispersechor is preeminently a constitutive property and much more sensitive to structural differences than the refrachor. Multiple linkages affect the dispersechor in the same direction, but to a much more marked extent than the refrachor. Among isomeric compounds, constitutional differences can be perceived more readily than by a comparison of the refrachor only. As this part of the work is only in a preliminary stage, nothing more can be said about it.

In collaboration with Shri A. R. Parikh and Miss N. K. Raisinghani, the author²² has communicated to the Indian Chemical Society, two papers in which the Sonochors (P_s) of over one hundred compounds have been examined. The *sonochor* is a functional

19. Gladstone and Dale, *Phil. Trans.*, 1959, 146, 887.

20. Lorentz and Lorenz, "Theoretical Chemistry", by W. Nernst, 6th ed. p. 311.

21. Joshi and Tuli, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 837.

22. Under publication.

constant of a liquid wherein the molecular volume is associated with ultrasonic velocity and is given by the relationship:

$$P_s = V^{3/10} \times V_m$$

M. R. Rao²³ was the first to study the relationship between the velocity of sound in a liquid (V), its density (D), and temperature, and found that $V^{1/3} = KD$, where K was independent of temperature. He had only eighteen liquids at his disposal to study and he did not take into consideration the orthobaric density of the vapour (d) of the liquid in correlating the ultrasonic velocity with the density of the liquid at different temperatures. From the considerable amount of data available on the ultrasonic velocities in different types of liquids at different temperatures, we have found that Rao's formula requires certain modification. If the correction is applied, the formula becomes

$$V^{3/10} = K(D-d)$$

where K is a constant, independent of temperature. Thus the sonochor (P_s) is given by

$$P_s = V^{3/10} \times V_m$$

The sonochors were obtained for over one hundred compounds belonging to different types, such as alkanes, alkenes, aromatic and hydroaromatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, phenols, ethers, aldehydes, ketones, esters, amines, alkyl and aryl halides, and nitriles. From the molecular sonochors, atomic sonochors for atoms like carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, halogens, and sulphur, and the nitro group and the structural effects of the double bond, the benzene ring and the cyclohexane ring were obtained. Table VII records the values of atomic and structural sonochors.

TABLE VII

Values of atomic and structural sonochors.

	Values.		Values.
Carbon	-30.0	S (ketonic)	265.7
Hydrogen	+89.0	Chlorine (aliphatic)	181.1
Methylene group (CH ₂)	148.0	Bromine (aliphatic)	178.0
Oxygen (OH)	6.8	Iodine (aliphatic)	224.4
Oxygen (phenolic)	21.8	Fluorine (aromatic)	105.7
Oxygen (ethereal)	54.0	Chlorine (aromatic)	194.2
Oxygen (ketonic)	171.5	Bromine (aromatic)	195.2
O ₂ in esters	223.0	N (in primary amine)	-18.8
Double bond	119.0	N (in nitriles)	239.9
Effect of benzene ring	55.8	N (in nitro group)	5.9
Effect of cyclohexane ring	28.8	NO ₂ group in aliphatic as well as aromatic compounds	231.4

The sonochor is generally additive in character, but constitutive effects are apparent in the case of oxygen, nitrogen, and halogens which show different values according to their

23. *Ind. J. Phys.*, 1940, 14, 109; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, 9, 682.

modes of linkage. Thus oxygen has different values according as it is in the form of a hydroxyl, either alcoholic or phenolic, an ether, a ketone or a carboxylate ester. The double bond, the benzene ring, and the cyclohexane ring show exaltation. The observed values of sonochors for different isomers belonging to the same series are different. Thus isomeric heptanes afford different values for *n*-heptane, 2-methylhexane, 2,2-dimethylpentane, 2,4-dimethylpentane, 3-methylhexane, 3-ethylpentane, and 3,3-dimethylpentane, the values decreasing in the order given. Similarly isomeric alcohols provide different values, the primary alcohols providing the highest and the tertiary alcohols, the lowest values as can be seen from the values of isomeric amyl, hexyl, and heptyl alcohols.

Nitrogen shows different values according to its nature of linkage, *i.e.*, whether it is present as a primary amino group or as a nitrile group or as a nitro group linked to aliphatic or aromatic radicals.

Surprisingly, interesting results are obtained with the halogens. Considering the monohalides, the atomic sonochors follow the order: iodine > chlorine > bromine > fluorine, as chlorine provides a higher value than bromine. An exaltation of the atomic sonochor of chlorine takes place when two chlorine atoms are present in a molecule, *e.g.* methylene dichloride, ethylene dichloride, propylene dichloride, and this exaltation becomes remarkable in the case of chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, and *sym*-tetrachloroethane. Similarly dibromo, tribromo and tetrabromo derivatives of aliphatic compounds show very high exaltation of the values of bromine, ranging from 7.2% to 17.2%.

A special significance attaches itself to the hydroxy compounds when the hydroxyl group is attached to allyl, benzyl, β -phenylethyl, γ -phenylpropyl, cyclohexyl, furylmethyl, and tetrahydrofurylmethyl groups, as exaltation in the value of the sonochor is observed. It is interesting to observe that the effect of the allyl and benzyl groups is almost identical, but that of β -phenylethyl and γ -phenylpropyl groups is also similar. Cyclohexane and specially the furane and tetrahydrofurane rings show an abnormal exaltation. In the present state of our knowledge, it is not possible to offer an adequate explanation of this anomaly. Among the aromatic halogen compounds, the three pairs (*a*) chlorobenzene and bromobenzene, (*b*) *o*-chlorotoluene and *o*-bromotoluene, (*c*) *p*-chlorotoluene and *p*-bromotoluene furnished almost identical values of sonochors. Again, the *para*-isomers provided higher values than *ortho*-isomers. The values of atomic sonochors for chlorine and bromine, when directly linked to an aryl group, though almost identical, are different from those obtainable when they are linked to an alkyl group. The sonochor for aryl bromine is one unit more than that of chlorine, whereas the alkyl chlorine has a higher value than that of bromine. The cause of these anomalies cannot be explained in the present state of our knowledge, though it may be traced to the question of the dipole moments of these compounds and its effect on ultrasonic velocities. More work is necessary on the problem. If the sonochor is a true measure of the molecular volume, there should be an intimate relationship among this constant, critical volume (V_c), Sugden's parachor (P), critical temperature (T_c), boiling point (T_b), and entropy (ΔS). These relationships are shown by

$$P_s = 1.94 \times \frac{V_c \times T_c}{T_b} = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta S} \times V_c \times T_c}{2.35 \times T_b}$$

Table VIII shows the relationship among the sonochor, Sugden's parachor, and critical volume.

TABLE VIII

Substance.	$[P_s]$.	V_c .	$[P]$.	P_s/V_c .	P/V_c .
Benzene	767.5	256.1	206.3	3.00	0.81
Diethyl ether	824.1	281.9	211.7	2.92	0.75
Ethyl acetate	823.6	286.0	217.1	2.95	0.76
<i>n</i> -Pentane	918.8	309.8	231.0	2.98	0.75
Propyl acetate	955.8	344.9	256.1	2.77	0.74
Carbon tetrachloride	750.4	276.1	219.9	2.72	0.80
Chlorobenzene	873.4	307.8	244.5	2.83	0.80
Cyclohexane	916.8	307.5	241.7	2.98	0.79
Acetone	616.6	216.6	161.7	2.85	0.75
			Mean	2.92	0.77

Table VIII shows that this ratio is approximately 2.92, though it varies slightly from substance to substance. The last column shows the ratio of Sugden's parachor to the critical volume. This is approximately 0.77, though it varies slightly from substance to substance. The mean collision areas (a) of four molecules are shown in Table VI.

If the sonochor is expressed according to Rao²³ in the form of a linear equation:

$$[P_s] = \alpha M + B$$

where M stands for the molecular weight of the liquid, the values of α , which is a *general constant* for all the series 10.57, and that of B , which is a *characteristic constant* for a particular homologous series, can be calculated. The calculated values for B are recorded in Table IX; these different values of P establish the structural effect of the sonochor. Moreover, the sonochor of any member of the series can be calculated from this equation.

TABLE IX

Series.	Values of B .	Series.	Values of B .
Alkanes	+155.8	Alkyl tetrachloride	-876.6
Alkenes	+120.3	Alkyl ketones	+2.6
Aromatic hydrocarbon	-58.2	Alkyl acids	-160.5
Aliphatic monohydric alcohols	-5.1	Alkyl ethers	+42.9
Aliphatic esters	-114.9	Alkyl cyanides	+13.5
Alkyl chlorides	-118.5	Alkyl nitro-	-177.1
Alkyl bromide	-588.7	sulphide	-301.9
Alkyl iodide	1039.6	Aryl chloride (mono)	-316.9
Alkylene dichloride	-381.6	Aryl bromide (mono)	-985.9
Alkyl trichloride	-624.9	Hydroaromatic hydrocarbon	+28.9

Finally, the sonochor is equally susceptible to constitutive influences, if not more than Sugden's parachor, and as its value is much bigger than that of the parachor, it is much easier to detect the constitutive factors in the molecule. It offers us a new method of comparing molecular volumes and of determining the molecular weight of non-associated liquids. Though some very admirable work on the ultrasonic velocity in liquids

has been done by Parthasarathy²⁴, Lagemann and co-workers²⁵, Weissler²⁶, and Freyer and co-workers²⁷, a considerable amount of work is necessary to apply this conception of sonochor to all types of liquids, as has been done in the case of Sugden's parachor. This should not be difficult in the near future as very sensitive methods of determining acoustic velocity in liquids have been developed. The values suggested for the atomic sonochors may undergo a slight modification in the light of better and more accurate values of ultrasonic velocity, but that does not detract from the merit of the fundamental nature of the work and the new approach.

The specific inductive capacity or dielectric constant (ϵ) is one of the important physical constants of a liquid and it decreases with temperature. The density of a liquid also decreases with temperature. For nonpolar liquids with low dielectric constant, such as aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons and symmetrically substituted aromatic hydrocarbons, the empirical relationship:

$$\epsilon^{5/3} = K (D-d)$$

where K is independent of temperature, holds good. Taking advantage of this equation, the author in collaboration with Shri A. R. Parikh and Miss N. K. Raisinghani has examined the possibility of using $(\epsilon^{5/3}) \times V_m = \text{a constant}$, which we have called *Inductochor* (P_ϵ) as a constant for nonpolar liquids. The values of atomic inductochor for carbon is 45.0 and for hydrogen, 7.5. The double bond shows the exaltation of 13.0, whereas five-membered and six-membered rings show the depression of 10 and 6 units. The data regarding the variation of the dielectric constant with temperature are rare and there is an ample scope for considerable work here.

Eötvös²⁸ deduced the general equation:

$$\gamma (Mv)^{2/3} = K (tc-t)^n$$

from the assumption that "bodies which are in corresponding states are also similar in mechanical respect, viz., in respect of the forces between their corresponding parts and their energies". He found that n was equal to 1 when surface tension was considered. This equation was modified by Ramsay and Shields²⁹, but the best modification was by Katayama³⁰ who gave it the form:

$$\gamma \left(\frac{M}{D-d} \right)^{2/3} = K(tc-t)^n$$

where $K = 2.1$ and $n = 1.0$ for normal liquids. This equation has provided one of the good methods of determining the molecular weights of normal liquids as well as the degree of association of associated liquids from a knowledge of surface tension (γ), densities of liquid

24. Parthasarathi *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12A**, 446.

25. Lagemann *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, **16**, 247; 1949, **17**, 396.

26. Weissler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1634.

27. Freyer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1929, **51**, 759.

28. Eötvös, *Ann. Physik*, 1886, **27**, 446.

29. Ramsay and Shields, *Phil. Trans.*, 1903, **184**, 647.

30. Katayama, *Sci. Rep. Tohyku Imp. Univ.*, 1916, **4**, 373.

(D) and vapour (d), and temperature (t). It is found in literature that this equation has so far been applied only to surface tension, but we have found that this equation can be applied to other forms of energy, viz., internal heat of vaporisation (λ_i), heat of vaporisation (λ), refractive index (n), velocity of sound in liquids (V), dielectric constant (ϵ), viscosity (η), vapour pressure (p), and fluidity (ϕ). The values of n and K are naturally different for each equation which holds good for normal liquids for temperature, ranging from zero to the critical temperature.

Forms of energy ..	γ	λ_i	λ	n	V	ϵ	η	p	ϕ
Value of n ..	1.0	0.25	0.22	0.1	0.8	0.02	2.8	10.2	3.2
Value of K ..	2.1	473.2	613.8	520.3	301.3	50.7	2.3×10^{-5}	28.0	..

From the knowledge of the application of the Hőtvös equation to various forms of energy or mechanical forces for one particular liquid, it is easy to correlate the values of different properties of the same liquid, *i.e.*, we can have a knowledge of the interrelationship existing among surface tension, latent heat of evaporation, refractive index, velocity of sound, dielectric constant, viscosity, fluidity, and vapour pressure. Moreover, just as surface tension has been utilised for the determination of molecular weight of normal liquids and degree of association, these other properties can also be utilised. It may be argued that these methods of approach are now old-fashioned, in comparison with the latest tools of investigation at the disposal of the chemists, viz., dipole moment, UV, IR, and Raman spectra; proton, electron, and neutron scatterings; NMR spectra, X-ray spectra etc., and that the physical interpretations of these equations are not given. I do grant the force of these arguments, but many private and university laboratories cannot afford these costly equipments, and for them such methods will always have an appeal. Moreover, it is an experienced fact that the tougher the disease, the tougher the remedy. Difficult structural problems do require highly developed techniques of investigation, but simple remedies are enough for simple difficulties. I request the physicists and physical chemists to help me in elucidating the physical interpretations.

SOME NEW OBSERVATIONS ON THE FRIEDEL-CRAFTS REACTION

The classical formula of benzene envisages a hexagon with three alternate double bonds, which are assumed to be in a constant state of oscillation between two forms A and B, though the recent physicochemical data do not furnish any evidence for the presence of alternate double and single bonds. The evidence for the double bond has been mainly chemical, such as ozonisation, catalytic reduction to cyclohexane, and addition of six atoms of halogens, etc.

Levine and Cole³¹ obtained, on ozonolysis of *o*-xylene, a mixture of glyoxal,

31. Levine and Cole, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 338.

methylglyoxal, and diacetyl in the ratio of 3:2:1, which is the same as calculated for a mixture of equal parts of the two Kekule forms of xylene (C) and (D).

A study of the substitution of resorcinol and its simple derivatives can show whether the localisation of double bonds can occur in simple benzene nucleus. The substitution in the resorcinol nucleus is an interesting problem in organic chemistry because of the industrial importance of certain resorcinol derivatives as intermediates for dyestuffs and synthetic drugs. As the two β -positions in resorcinol are more reactive than the γ -position, mono-substitution occurs in β position only. The only known case of γ -substitution in the case of resorcinol is the observation of Michael³² that the application of the Nencki reaction to a mixture of resorcinol and salicylic acid furnishes 1-hydroxyxanthone. Orcinol underwent the Pechmann reaction with open-chain as well as cyclic β -ketones, providing 5-hydroxycoumarins (γ -substitution), as observed by Dey³³ and Ahmad and Desai³⁴, and the Nencki reaction with salicylic acid, affording 1-hydroxyxanthone derivatives as observed by Michael. After one β -position of the resorcinol nucleus is substituted, the second group may enter the β - or γ -position. Baker and his collaborators³⁵ found that the 4-allyl ether of resacetophenone underwent the Claisen rearrangement, providing 3-allylresacetophenone (γ -substitution), whereas its methyl ether afforded 5-allyl-2-*O*-methylresacetophenone (β -substitution). The Fries migration of 4-*O*-acetylresacetophenone furnished a mixture of 2,4- and 4,6-diacetylresorcinol (β - and γ -substitution), but its methyl ether provided only 4,6-diacetyl derivative (β -substitution). Desai and his co-workers³⁶ found that the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of resacetophenone and orcinol furnished a mixture of β - and γ -substitution products. Similarly definite and conclusive evidence of simultaneous β - and γ -substitution or γ -substitution alone was obtained in the case of the reaction between β -orcacetophenone and acetic anhydride, resacetophenone and benzoyl chloride as well as 4-benzoylresorcinol and acetic anhydride. The action of propionic and butyric anhydrides on orcinol provided the exclusive γ -substitution. Trivedi and Sethna³⁷ acetylated, propionylated, benzoylated, and succinoylated β -methyl resoreylate, obtaining the evidence for simultaneous β - and γ -substitution. Thus one can conclude that γ -substitution can occur in the derivatives of resorcinol if there is a chelation of one of the hydroxyl groups with an acetyl, benzoyl, or carbomethyl groups in the *ortho* position or due to steric hindrance, as in the case of orcinol. R. C. Shah and co-workers³⁸ also obtained evidence of either exclusive γ -substitution or simultaneous β - and γ -substitution by the study of the Gattermann, Pechmann, and Friedel-Crafts reactions in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

The application of anhydrous aluminium chloride for the rearrangement of the aryl esters of aliphatic and aromatic acids, known as the Fries reaction, has been studied by a number of investigators from various points of view, but the mechanism of this reaction

32. Michael, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1883, 5, 81.

33. Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1614.

34. Ahmad and Desai, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 277.

35. Baker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 628; 1936, 274; 1934, 1664; 1937, 479.

36. Trivedi and Sethia *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 8A, 194; 1940, 12A, 391; 1947, 15A, 364.

37. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 245; 1952, 29, 141.

38. Shah *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 238, 1224, 1828; 1939, 132, 300, 949; 1940, 245; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 29A, 227.

has remained mysterious. Rosenmund and Schnurr³⁹ proposed the intermolecular mechanism, whereas Auwers and Mauss⁴⁰ advocated the intramolecular rearrangement mechanism. The author in collaboration with C. K. Mavani⁴¹ carried out a few experiments to ascertain the mechanism of the Fries reaction. On heating a mixture of hydroquinone diacetate, resorcinol, and anhydrous aluminium chloride, the main products obtained were resacetophenone, 2, 4-diacetylresorcinol, only a trace of quinacetophenone being obtained. This rules out the intramolecular rearrangement mechanism of Auwers and Mauss⁴⁰, as it would have provided an appreciable amount of quinacetophenone. Moreover, when resorcinol diacetate was heated with aluminium chloride, a mixture of resacetophenone, 2,4-diacetylresorcinol, and some resacetophenone diacetate was formed. The isolation of the last substance showed that it must have been initially formed by acetylation of one molecule of resorcinol diacetate by another molecule. Thus the intermolecular mechanism of Rosenmund and Schnurr, wherein one molecule of the ester serves to acylate the second molecule, is amply supported. As the literature with the exception of Rittler's patents⁴² was very scanty with regard to the rearrangement of the aryl esters of aromatic sulphonic acids, the author in collaboration with J. H. Amin⁴³ studied the Fries migration of the aryl *p*-toluenesulphonates of phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, etc. at 130-140°. The migration was smooth at this temperature, providing a convenient method for the synthesis of hydroxydiaryl sulphones which are useful as antiseptics and dyestuff intermediates. It must be stated at the outset that the aryl esters of alkylsulphonic acids do not undergo this rearrangement. Moreover, the aryl sulphonates require higher temperatures for rearrangement as compared with aryl carboxylates. Investigations of the aryl esters of α - and β -naphthylsulphonic acids with Shri A. R. Parikh⁴⁴ showed that the former esters provided mainly the *ortho*-substitution, whereas the latter yielded *para*-substitution products. This work has also been extended to *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo-, and *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonic acids. A study of the Fries migration of 4-methylcoumarinyl-7-*p*-toluenesulphonate with Miss M. D. Bhavsar⁴⁵ provided 7-hydroxy-4-methylchlorocoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-*p*-toluenesulphonyl-4-methylcoumarin in absence of a solvent. Anhydrous aluminium chloride functioned as the chlorinating agent. It remains to be seen whether this is a general reaction. When the reaction was carried out in nitrobenzene solution, the mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-*p*- and 8-*p*-toluenesulphonyl-4-methylcoumarins was obtained in the proportion of 2:1. This was in striking contrast with the Fries migration of 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin which provided mainly the 8-acetyl derivative, whereas the isomeric 6-acetyl derivative was formed in a small amount. The sulphonates of 5-hydroxycoumarins underwent the migration readily, affording the 6-*p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative, but the sulphonates of 6-hydroxycoumarins did not undergo the migration under any conditions. This result is consistent with the observation of the author and C. K. Mavani⁴⁶ that the acetate of 6-hydroxycoumarin does not undergo the migration. The Fries migration of the

39. Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, **460**, 56.

40. Auwers and Mauss, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 1495.

41. Desai and Mavani, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12B**, 236.

42. Rittler, D. R. Pat. 532403 and 555409 (1931); *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, **26**, 153, 5105.

43. Amin and Desai, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, **13B**, 181.

44. Desai and Parikh, unpublished work.

45. Bhabani and Desai, *This Journal*, 1954, **31**, 167.

46. Desai and Mavani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, **15A**, 11; 1947, **25A**, 327.

aryl esters of arylsulphonic acids has recently been carried out also by V. Baliah and his co-workers⁴⁷.

Lastly, it has been observed by the author in collaboration with Miss S. K. Dalal⁴⁸ that the amino groups of 1-amino- and 2-amino-anthraquinones condense smoothly with phenyl isothiocyanate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, providing 1-anthraquinonyl- and 2-anthraquinonyl-phenylthioureas which behave as vat dyes like the algal vat dyes of the anthraquinone series. Whereas phenyl isocyanate condensed readily at high temperature with the amino groups of 1-amino- and 2-amino-anthraquinones, the sulphur analogue required the catalytic action of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The reaction went smoothly with 1,4-, 1,5- and 2,6-diaminoanthraquinones. In an effort to study this reaction with anthraquinone, it was noticed that anthraquinone itself underwent some complex condensation, affording a reddish violet dye, the constitution of which is under investigation. This reaction seems to be general, as substituted anthraquinones also provide similar types of dyes varying in shade from reddish brown to reddish violet. The deep shades of these dyestuffs as well as their facile vattability are against the constitution of their being the derivatives of di- or tri-anthraquinonyl *ms*-benzodianthrone or *ms*-naphthodianthrone derivatives. In all probability, these are the derivatives of dibenzo-perylenequinone, the dyestuff from anthraquinone being probably formed as shown below and may be 5,6,11,12-dibenzoperylene-4,10-quinone.

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47. Baliah *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 513; 1955, **32**, 773; 1956, **33**, 189; 1957, **34**, 58; 1959, **36**, 391.

48. Desai and Dalal, unpublished work.